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Abstract

ConcePTION aims to develop an ecosystem that can efficiently, systematically, and in an ethically responsible manner generate and disseminate reliable evidence-based information regarding effects of medications used in pregnancy and breastfeeding. The approach of ConcePTION is similar to what is being called a Learning Healthcare System (LHS) in the literature. In an LHS, care and research are aligned to accelerate research and outcomes for patients. Furthermore, an LHS aims to systematically study, evaluate and improve quality and efficiency of care while speeding up the process of generating generalizable medical evidence. Taking an LHS approach to knowledge generation in the field of pregnancy and breastfeeding may broaden the opportunities to strengthen the evidence base, among others by learning from routinely collected data. However, applying an LHS approach to the field of pregnancy and breastfeeding comes with ethical challenges. In this report we present an ethics framework and discuss important ethical principles to overcome these issues and to help guide the development of an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people, which in turn could be used for the development of the ConcePTION ecosystem.

Methods

For the development of an ethics framework, we took an approach in which stakeholders' perspectives as well as ethical theory are translated in the context of ConcePTION as an LHS. We conducted in depth interviews with cisgender women during preconception, pregnancy and nursing to collect their views on an ethically responsible LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people. Furthermore, we studied literature on LHSs, on research with pregnant and breastfeeding people, and on existing ethics frameworks for (learning) health systems and public health ethics. We incorporated these approaches into our ethical reasoning.

Results

Our report offers an ethics framework which contains principles that stimulate the change towards an LHS, the development of an LHS, and the responsible implementation of an LHS in the field of pregnant and breastfeeding people. In our framework, we put emphasis on the principles of solidarity, justice, equity and responsiveness, respect for autonomy, trust, transparency and responsibility and sustainability. We also explain the importance of a change in the way knowledge is being generated, and how the development of an LHS can overcome current struggles in knowledge generation for pregnant and breastfeeding people. Furthermore, our report visualizes ConcePTION as an LHS and provides insights into how the ethical principles can be implemented in the ConcePTION ecosystem.

Conclusion

The development of an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people does not come without challenges. Our ethics framework responds to these challenges and guides the development of an ethically responsible and sustainable LHS. We emphasize that it is important that all stakeholders support the idea that we need to change the way knowledge is currently being generated and that it is crucial to develop ways to share new knowledge with pregnant and breastfeeding people in order to really improve clinical practice.

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Introduction

The goal of this deliverable is to present an ethics framework for a responsible and sustainable Learning Healthcare System (LHS) for pregnant and breastfeeding people. This framework is relevant to ConcePTION. ConcePTION aims to develop a trusted ecosystem that can efficiently, systematically, and in an ethically responsible manner, generate and disseminate reliable evidence-based information regarding effects of medications used in pregnancy and breastfeeding. The approach of this envisioned ecosystem is similar to what is being called an LHS in the literature.

In an LHS, care and research are aligned to accelerate research and outcomes for patients and to overcome current problems, such as low inclusion rates and complex informed consent procedures. LHSs aim to systematically study, evaluate and improve quality and efficiency of care while speeding up the process of generating generalizable medical evidence for pregnant and breastfeeding people. The purpose of LHSs range from optimizing clinical care by learning from routinely collected data to embedding randomized controlled trials (RCTs) in routine clinical care (Wouters et al., 2020). Since RCTs with pregnant and breastfeeding people hardly ever take place, because investigators often choose to exclude pregnant and breastfeeding people and their newborns from research, learning from routinely collected health data is a method that needs to be taken seriously if we want to realize change in the way knowledge is currently generated. Taking an LHS approach to knowledge generation in the field of pregnancy and breastfeeding may broaden the opportunities to strengthen the evidence base, by learning from routinely collected data. However, applying an LHS approach to the field of pregnancy and breastfeeding comes with ethical challenges.

Since the aim of ConcePTION is to build a knowledge generating ecosystem, which has similarities with the method of an LHS, this report is focused on the development of an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people. Furthermore, this report will discuss the opportunities and challenges and provides for an overview of ethical principles that are important for the development of a sustainable and ethically responsible LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people

To develop an ethics framework, we took an approach in which stakeholders' perspectives as well as ethical theory on principles such as responsibility, solidarity, equity and fairness are translated in the context of ConcePTION as an LHS.

Structure of the report

First, we briefly discuss what LHSs are including its most important elements and describe the (ethical and methodological) challenges that an LHS approach raises. To overcome the challenges and to support the transformation of ConcePTION to an LHS, we developed an ethics framework that will emphasize ethical principles to advance LHSs for pregnant and breastfeeding people. In this deliverable the ethical principles formulated in the framework will be provided with a commentary based on the research we have done for this project. Besides a commentary, this report will also show how ConcePTION can be understood as an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people, as well as, provide concrete steps for the ConcePTION project towards the development of an LHS.

Furthermore, in this report we will refer to pregnant and breastfeeding *people* instead of *women*, to be more inclusive of all different people affected by the lack of knowledge on medication safety and efficacy during pregnancy and breastfeeding. With that, in the literature more and more authors from various disciplines have started to use pregnant *people* instead of pregnant *women*. For example, in the literature on the (lack of) research with pregnant people on the safety of the Covid-19 vaccines, ethics literature and the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) and the World Health Organisation in their new guidance document *Ethical Considerations in HIV Prevention Trials*. This argument will be explained in more detail under 2.2.2 *Justice, equity and responsiveness* (p. 16).

Methods

For the development of an ethics framework for an ethically responsible and sustainable LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people, we took an approach in which stakeholders' perspectives as well as ethical theory are translated in the context of ConcePTION as an LHS. Thus, our approach has empirical, analytical and conceptual elements. In this report, we bring these three elements together and aim to produce coherence between empirical, conceptual and normative data. The moral intuitions from our empirical research and the ethical principles and general theories from our analytical and conceptual approach, are incorporated in our ethical reasoning.

Empirical approach

For the empirical approach, we employed a qualitative study design to explore people's views on an ethically responsible LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people (Hollestelle et al., 2022). Our study focused solely on people during preconception, pregnancy and nursing, since we were interested in the primary target population of the LHS specifically, which accordingly could be aligned with the opinion of other relevant stakeholders within the ConcePTION-project.

Design

We performed semi-structured interviews with a topic list (see Table 1), which came from two sources. We used some of the items from guideline 12 of the 2016 Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans (CIOMS, 2016). The CIOMS guideline 12 covers essential elements for governing the collection, storage, and analysis of data in health-related research. A parallel can be drawn between data analysis within an LHS and health-related research in general, and therefore, the CIOMS guideline is very relevant for an LHS. We also used the results of a narrative review on patient and public views and attitudes towards the sharing of health data for research (Kalkman et al., 2019). This review gave insight into key conditions for the use of health data in general, which were used as topics in the interviews.

Table 1 *General topic list*

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1. Attitude towards the status quo and the goal of ConcePTION
 2. Participatory engagement
 3. Respect for autonomy
 4. Perceived risks
 5. Need for return of results
 6. Inclusion and freeriding
 7. Sustainability
-

Sample and setting

We aimed to include people whose data may become part of an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people. We therefore included people who wanted to become pregnant, were pregnant at the time of the interview, or were nursing up to 6 months after giving birth. Furthermore, to obtain a broad range of perspectives on the topics, we aimed to include people with different medical backgrounds and diverse characteristics. Respondents were recruited by purposeful sampling with the help of our contact persons from the University Medical Center Utrecht, the Amsterdam University Medical Center, The Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Center Lareb, Eurocat Northern Netherlands, and by means of snowball sampling. Potential respondents were then approached and informed about the set-up of the study by e-mail or by phone.

Data collection and analysis

The semi-structured interviews were conducted with a topic list. According to the technique of constant comparative analysis, the interview topics evolved as the interviews progressed alongside the data analysis (Charmaz, 2006). We analyzed the interviews by going back and forth between data collection and analysis to develop codes with software program NVivo 12. We compared, (re)labelled, and added codes to the coding list, and formulated higher order themes.

A total of 20 semi-structured interviews were conducted with people who varied in medical indication, stage of pregnancy and reproductive history.

More details on our empirical study can be found in the publication called: *A Learning Healthcare System for pregnant and breastfeeding women: what do women during preconception, pregnancy, and nursing think? – A qualitative study (2022)* in BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth (pp.1-12).

Analytical and conceptual approach

The analytical approach consisted of a literature study and conceptual analysis. The goal of our literature study was to understand the relevant ethical questions that arise in a sustainable and ethically responsible LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people. As a theoretical framework, we utilized conventional ethical principles for care and research as well as for (learning) health systems. As mentioned earlier, in an LHS, care and research are integrated. This integrated structure may raise questions about, for example: the way informed consent is obtained, the degree of patient participation once a learning element is being added to care. Before we explored the ethical issues in relation to an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people, we thought about what an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding would look like. To be able to envision an LHS for this specific group we explored the literature on LHSs and used the ConcePTION Ecosystem to uncover both important stakeholders and relevant procedures. Furthermore, we turned to the existing literature on (bio)ethical frameworks for LHSs, health systems and public health ethics to explore which core principles, values and considerations are put forth. Through our conceptual explorations, we also sought to identify particular areas of convergence for ethical principles related to the field of pregnant and breastfeeding people as well as to projects that aim to learn from real-world (health) data. Our conceptual explorations also led to a more in depth conceptual analysis of certain principles (incorporated in the ethics framework).

The findings from both the empirical, analytical and conceptual research were used to inform our ethics framework for an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people. Through reflection and thinking more about how to build a sustainable and ethically responsible LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people, we present a working ethics framework with an LHS perspective. The principles described in the ethical framework can be used by the ConcePTION network for the development of a sustainable and ethically responsible ecosystem of continuous learning.

Results

1.1 Towards a Learning Healthcare system for pregnant and breastfeeding people

In real life, numerous medications have been used safely and effectively in pregnancy with minimal risk to the fetus and mother, but we are not systematically learning from these experiences (Adam, Polifka & Friedman, 2011; IMI ConcePTION, 2020). There are strong ethical reasons to change the way evidence is currently being generated and disseminated. In the literature, multiple solutions for increasing the evidence base for medications for pregnant people have been suggested, such as, routine inclusion of pregnant people in clinical trials or the use of an adaptive trial design to support safe and efficient inclusion of pregnant people in different stages of medication development (Baylis, 2010; Roes et al., 2018). However, pregnant people hesitate to participate in trials, and medicines

manufacturers hesitate to have them included, because of potential liability issues (van der Graaf et al., 2018). Given the vast availability of real-world data on medicines prescriptions and health outcomes, an alternative way to generate evidence is to learn from previous and current medication use, by transforming the field of care for pregnant and breastfeeding people into a Learning Healthcare System (LHS) (van der Graaf et al., 2019). As explained before, in an LHS, healthcare and research are aligned to accelerate research and outcomes for patients. LHSs have the potential to develop scientific knowledge based on health information and research data, and by directly implementing new insights from analyses to the clinical practice (Foley & Fairmichael, 2015).

Currently, information on the safety and efficacy of medications used during pregnancy and breastfeeding is fragmented and spread across different data sources, pregnancy or medicines cohorts, registries, and research groups with unique data regarding pregnancies, adverse drug reactions and the like. Examples are the European system for the evaluation of safety of medication use in pregnancy in relation to risk of congenital anomalies (EUROmediCAT) and the European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS). Combining these unique data sources into a system of continuous learning could help clarify how medications impact pregnancy outcomes and breastfeeding exposures (van der Graaf et al., 2019; IMI ConcePTION).

1.2 Learning Healthcare Systems

The concept of LHSs has emerged in multiple areas of healthcare over the recent years as a strategy to improve the quality of care and research by using experiences from clinical care and practice (Foley & Fairmichael, 2015). The idea is that in an LHS research and care are no longer separated, which should help evaluate and improve quality and efficiency of care while speeding up the process of generating generalizable medical evidence (Wouters et al., 2021). In essence, all LHSs are continuous cycles of data collection, data analysis, interpretation of results, feedback, implementation of results in daily care, new (research) questions (see figure 1).

Figure 1 Abstract representation of a Learning Healthcare System Cycle

The concept of an LHS is not uniform, and proposals to achieve such a cycle of continuous learning range from optimizing clinical care by learning from routinely collected data to embedding randomized controlled trials (RCTs) in routine clinical care. In a paper by Wouters et al, different models of LHSs are described that explain the different ways of how research and care can become integrated (Wouters et al., 2020). There is model 1, called the optimization learning healthcare system, which

aims to optimize conditions within care and research to create an environment that encourages patients to participate in research and professionals to translate scientific insights into clinical practice. The second model, called the comprehensive data learning healthcare system, aims to generate evidence by routinely collecting and processing vast quantities of clinical data. Model 3, called the real-time learning health care system aims to provide real-time feedback of data analysis at the point of care. Lastly, model 4, which can be described as a full learning healthcare system, aims to fully integrate research and care to the point that clinical care is remodeled on research principles and that the care delivery process becomes a prospective interventional trial (Wouters et al., 2020).

We believe that similarities can be drawn between the ConcePTION ecosystem and the model 2 type LHS. Therefore, in this report, we focus mainly on the type of LHS that aims to optimize clinical care and reproductive decision-making by learning from routinely collected health data and data specifically collected for research. Furthermore, research within this model, remains nonexperimental, because the care that individual patients will receive is not directly affected by the process of collecting and analyzing the data involved (Wouters et al, 2020).

1.3 What does an LHS for pregnant people look like?

Ideally, an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people would entail data collection and data analysis, for the purpose of helping people and their physicians to make an informed decision about whether to start, continue or stop a certain treatment. This means that new insights from data analysis flow back to the patients and their physician. But it also means that ideally, patients and their physicians can use the LHS to ask (new) safety questions.

In principle, an LHS consists of an inward and outward flow. The inward flow represents the assembling of data from various sources, like for example clinical care and registries, and the outward flow represents the findings from data analyses that potentially change clinical practice or pose new research questions (Friedman in Steels & Staa, 2019). The outward flow can also be understood as *learning activities*. Learning activities are the results of the interpretation of the results from data analyses. Learning activities can, therefore, be clear objectives for how to improve clinical practice, but they can also represent new knowledge for pregnant people to inform themselves with, or they can pose new research questions or findings that stimulate new research.

Inward flow

Ideally, the inward flow of an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people contains all relevant data on medication safety and efficacy in pregnancy and breastfeeding. Examples of existing data sources, are: healthcare data, registries (i.e. pregnancy related registries, birth registries, registries for the epidemiological surveillance), teratology information service (TIS) data, pharmacovigilance centers, databases of the pharmaceutical industry. These data sources can be roughly divided into five categories: 1) signaling, 2) register, 3) TIS, 4) research, 5) quality improvement. All these data sources produce different type of data regarding the effects of medication used before, during and after a pregnancy.

Outward flow or feedback loop

New insights resulting from the analyses conducted with the help of these databases need to flow back to practice. How new insights flow back can happen through multiple ways: for example, it may reach patients and their physicians through public knowledge services, through updated drug labels or through scientific papers based on data analyses within the LHS. New findings can also lead to more research questions and therefore stimulating research with pregnant and breastfeeding people. Lastly, new insights can potentially be used to improve care, which in turn, can be learned from when new data will be collected from the clinical practice.

Stakeholders

The shift towards an LHS approach has impact on many different stakeholders. Furthermore, to realize the transformation to an LHS requires multi-stakeholder involvement. Pharma, HCPs, patients, funders, regulators and others should all support the idea that we have to change the current paradigm of knowledge generation in the field of pregnancy and breastfeeding (van der Graaf et al., 2019). With that, we can also identify some aspects of the LHS in which certain stakeholders have a more prominent role. For example, pregnant and breastfeeding people, HCPs and researchers are the ones who are affected by learning activities and play a vital role in the inward flow of the LHS. Researchers, data access providers, health institutions are involved in setting up the LHS and providing relevant data to be utilized. Funders and research agenda setters are involved in making sure research can be carried out with sufficient funds and support. HCPs, researchers, health institutions, pharma, regulators are involved in developing ways to disseminate new knowledge and implement new information into clinical practice or existing sources of information (for example: drug labels).

Advantages of an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people and their HCP

Currently, patients and HCPs are uncertain whether to stop or continue medication since evidence is limited. Right now, the information on medication safety is scattered, non-existent, or contradictory, leading to withholding or discontinuation of treatments, which is just as or even more problematic when someone is well adjusted to a medication. Discontinuation can lead to a serious flare-up of the disease, putting the patient and their fetus at risk. An LHS creates the advantage to organize and optimize the information on medication safety and efficacy during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

Another advantage of an LHS is that it creates the opportunity to systematically learn from all current medication use. Whether it concerns medication for chronic diseases or conditions, obstetrical complications, or acute illnesses, pregnant people use at least 1 to 3 medications during pregnancy. Collecting and learning from all these experiences will help strengthen the evidence base on which new insights can be based.

In addition, an LHS provides a solution for the ethical problem of over-protecting pregnant people in low-risk research and under-protecting patients exposed to high-risk treatments in healthcare. Two now classic cases have changed the way we perceive risk during pregnancy. From experiences with drugs like Thalidomide and diethylstilboestrol (DES), but also more recently with Sildenafil citrate (used in the STRIDER study), we know that prescribing drugs with little knowledge on safety and efficacy is not without risks. In the 1950s, thalidomide was prescribed to pregnant people to treat nausea, without prior safety studies having been completed. Prescribing Thalidomide resulted in severe birth defects in over 10000 children (Baylis & Ballantyne, 2016; Macklin, 2010). DES was prescribed from 1940s-1960s to millions of pregnant people to prevent miscarriage. In 1971, DES was linked to several adverse effects, including vaginal and cervical cancer in young women exposed to DES during foetal development (Baylis & Ballantyne, 2016; Swan, 2001). From 2015, Sildenafil was given to pregnant people to treat fetal growth restriction and preeclampsia. Former studies had shown that there was a positive effect of Sildenafil on fetal growth, however, the first results from the study in 2015 showed that the drug may have caused negative outcomes for the babies after birth (Amsterdam UMC, 2018). These events may have resulted in a reluctance to include pregnant people in research, however, these events also show that we must consider the risks of not conducting research in pregnant people: prescription of treatments for pregnant people without systematic assessment first (van der Zande et al., 2021). Moreover, Sildenafil had already been prescribed by doctors around the world, it was only because of the STRIDER study that the potential adverse outcomes have been flagged (Browne et al., 2018).

Transforming the field of pregnant and breastfeeding people into an LHS is a promising way forward, especially with the proven ability of learning from Real World Data (RWD).

1.4 Methodological and ethical challenges

Despite the promises to improve clinical care and accelerate scientific research, transforming the healthcare system of pregnant and breastfeeding people into an LHS raises challenges. These challenges range from methodological to ethical challenges.

Methodologically, an LHS raises questions concerning the completeness of the data. For example, health data is often distributed across multiple organizations, and might offer limited access to a complete clinical picture. Furthermore, using data from multiple different types of organizations from different countries is also challenging because of its heterogeneity and often unstructured form (Basole et al., 2015). Another challenge concerns the qualification of learning activities as (scientific) research. Because these learning activities are highly dependent on the quality, usability and value of the data, and therefore, the findings from the analyses with the data. More challenges arise in the case of missing or inaccurate variables or when there is a lack of context (i.e. information on a population, country, disease, and health system) to validate findings (Cribb, Entwistle and Mitchell, 2019). Also, the individual translation of results will be limited, since some analyses will still be based on a small population or lack a control-group. It is important to think about how new results flow back into practice and how to make sure the inward flow of the LHS is protected (meaning that new data is being collected after the implementation of new insights from analyses from the LHS) as well as the validity of these results.

If an LHS is able to realize the continuous improvement of care for pregnant and breastfeeding people and thereby reduce risk of harm, increase health, improve information on medication safety, it would already fulfil some of the core principles of health care (Beauchamp & Childress, 2001). However, transitioning to an LHS raises ethical challenges that also need an “ethical” response.

First of all, an LHS challenges the traditional ways of ethically and legally evaluating care and research. Medical research is typically bound to different sets of ethical, legal and procedural norms than care (Wouters et al., 2021). Furthermore, it raises the question whether research-oriented activities within an LHS should be governed according to care or research norms. With that, it raises the question when participants should be informed and asked for informed consent. Literature provides a range of options that may be justifiable alternatives to traditional informed consent, such as specific or opt-in consent for research activities or data collection within an LHS (Wouters et al., 2021). Alternatives to traditional informed consent include changes to the form (oral instead of written), substance (broad informed consent instead of specific informed consent) or default (opt-out instead of opt-in) (Wouters et al., 2021; Angrist et al., 2015). Nonetheless, alternative forms of consent should also be in accordance with national and international laws and regulations. Furthermore, empirical evidence suggests that many patients expect some form of consent for research, and are even sometimes uncomfortable with deidentified research (Spector-Bagdady & Jagsi, 2018; Hollestelle, et al., 2022).

Second, an LHS also puts pressure on the patient-doctor relationship. A systematic review by McLennan et al. (2018), identified different issues related to the role of the physician in an LHS. These issues were described as possible conflict between the physician’s independence and evidence-based medicine. In other words, within an LHS the question arises when a physicians can deviate from the results generated through the LHS. Furthermore, it was mentioned that the traditional role of the physician might change because of the LHS, since there are now other resources available, perhaps accessible to both patient and physician. Our interviews also show that people have certain wishes regarding the dissemination of information in which the role of the physician is important in translating new information to individuals, hoping to receive a ‘yes’ or ‘no’ answer. Furthermore, the role of the physician might also change because of the integration of clinical research and clinical practice. For both clinical practice and clinical research there are ethics frameworks to which physicians and researchers must adhere to. For example, in clinical practice the physician has a responsibility towards the mother and foetus. In clinical research, the generalizability of results needs

to be protected (Brody & Miller, 2003). Combining these responsibilities in an LHS might be challenging, even when the outcome of the integration of practice and research seems promising for the group of pregnant and breastfeeding people, particularly when these people are dependent on medication use because of a chronic disease.

Third, an LHS complicates the risk-benefit balance for patients. Up to now, the current health system is grounded in an assumption that research must be separated from clinical care because researchers work towards generalizable knowledge as opposed to the best interest of the patient. Therefore, research participants require additional protections. However, as mentioned earlier, in the case of pregnant people, we have moved to a system where participants are protected from risk in research to the extent that these protections may lead to risks in clinical care (Spectator-Bagdady & Jagsi, 2018). Currently, there is tension between providing best clinical care and being able to study what the standard of care should actually be. In an LHS this tension can lead to both overreliance on regulatory expectations that are poorly understood and a lack of transparency regarding learning activities (Spectator-Bagdady & Jagsi, 2018).

Fourth, transforming the field of pregnant and breastfeeding people into an LHS will, besides overcoming the above-mentioned ethical issues, also depend on the support of a broad range of key stakeholders within the health system (Moloney et al., 2016). For example, people of childbearing age need to trust there is significant value and quality in the alternative approach so that they can rely on this evidence, and they need to believe their concerns about this new approach are taken seriously (Moloney et al., 2016). An LHS depends on collaboration and engagement to really improve health care and health outcomes. To achieve collaboration and engagement is challenging, since most pregnant and breastfeeding people will not or to a limited extent understand the concept of an LHS, as became apparent during our interview-study.

The development of an ethically sound LHS is complex and faces many challenges. Therefore, as mentioned earlier, the ethical challenges described above do not just need a practical solution, but need an ethical response. To respond to the ethical challenges, this report presents an ethics framework with important ethical principles that can help guide the development of an ethically responsible and sustainable LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people as well as provide a response to the identified ethical challenges.

2.1 Ethics Framework

In the literature, the main proposed ethics framework for an LHS, is the one developed by Faden et al. (2013). Their framework (see table 2) is formulated to help guide health care systems towards LHSs and to overcome the contradiction between clinical research ethics and clinical practice ethics when research and practice merge. Faden and colleagues also emphasize the ethical obligations for researchers, clinicians and patients to “feed information into the system that increases our knowledge” (Faden 2013). However, it has been argued in past empirical research that patients generally do not recognize such an obligation (Spectator-Bagdady & Jagsi, 2018). It is our belief that an obligation is too strong because it overrules some relevant individual rights that we believe should not be challenged, such as the right to individual integrity and autonomy. For our framework we acknowledge their work, and formulate more specific principles for a specific LHS, namely an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people. We also learned from the conceptual exploration of ethics principles for a framework for health systems, developed by Krubiner and Hyder (2014). Their aim was to explore a broader ethical framework for moral issues at the level of health systems. In their paper, they discuss morally relevant considerations (see table 3) that should be used to guide policies and actions targeting health system improvements and innovations.

Table 2 Learning Health Care system Ethics Framework by Faden et al

Obligation	Parties bearing the obligation
To respect the rights and dignity of patients	Researchers, clinicians, health care systems administrators, payers, purchasers
To respect the clinical judgement of clinicians	Researchers, health care systems administrators, payers, purchasers
To provide optimal care to each patient	Researchers, clinicians, health care systems administrators, payers, purchasers
Avoid imposing nonclinical risks and burdens on patients	Researchers, clinicians, health care systems administrators, payers, purchasers
Address health inequalities	Researchers, clinicians, health care systems administrators, payers, purchasers
Conduct continuous learning activities that improve the quality of clinical care and health care systems	Researchers, clinicians, health care systems administrators, payers, purchasers
Contribute to the common purpose of improving the quality and value of clinical care and health care systems	Patients

Table 3 Candidate considerations for health systems ethics by Krubiner & Hyder

1. Holism
2. Sustainability
3. Evidence and effectiveness
4. Efficiency
5. Public engagement and transparency
6. Accountability and feedback
7. Equity and empowerment
8. Justice and fairness

-
9. Responsiveness
 10. Collaboration
 11. Quality
-

Since our report mainly concerns the development of a learning healthcare system for the group of pregnant and breastfeeding people, we try to make the principles in our framework more specific to that of the LHS context. Some of our principles were discussed or presented during consortium meetings and conference talks, to further discuss and explore them.

We first present the framework (see table 4). The framework contains principles followed by a normative statement regarding the obligations that follow from that principle, including the stakeholders who should bear the obligation. The framework will then be followed by a more in-depth commentary on the principles. The commentary describes why these principles are important and how they ought to be interpreted in the context of an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people. In the commentary we ethically reflect upon the principles and connect our conceptual approach with our empirical study.

The principles also capture the narrative of why it is important to develop an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people, as well as the necessary requirements for the development and responsible implementation of an LHS. To elaborate, this framework starts (just like this report) from the position that there is an ethical imperative to change the way knowledge is currently being generated regarding the safety and efficacy of medication used during pregnancy and breastfeeding. To stimulate the much needed change and to offer a new perspective on how change can be initiated, we introduce the principle of solidarity. Solidarity among both pregnant and breastfeeding people and among researchers, healthcare professionals and funders could be of great importance in changing the status quo. With the principle of solidarity, we appeal to the role of pregnant and breastfeeding people themselves in closing the knowledge gap through the ways of an LHS. Furthermore, in the literature on ethics frameworks for health systems, much attention is drawn to collaboration with and empowerment of patients and the stimulation of public engagement to help guide the development of an ethically and sustainable (learning) health system (Krubiner & Hyder, 2014; Faden et al., 2013; Moloney et al., 2016).

For the development of an LHS, we want to draw attention to the principles of justice, equity and responsiveness. These principles are important for making sure that the true health needs of all pregnant and breastfeeding people, also inclusive to all gender, ethnicities, ages, socio-economic backgrounds, and medical conditions are considered in designing the LHS and in the inward and outward flow of the LHS. The issues of stimulating equal access to necessary health goods and the mitigation of disparities across populations, are considered extremely important in the literature on ethics of health systems. Moreover, in the literature and beyond it has been commonly described that the situation for pregnant and breastfeeding people is far from just. Developing an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people, also means to address the principles of justice, equity and responsiveness, to really change the situation for this group.

To stimulate responsible implementation of an LHS, we want to stress the importance of the principles of respect for autonomy, trust, transparency, responsibility and sustainability. These principles are also important to consider during the developmental phase of the LHS, but we want to emphasize their importance during the implementation phase. Once an LHS is developed, it needs to be clear to all relevant stakeholders what purpose the LHS fulfills, but more importantly it needs to be clear how the LHS works, in order for all stakeholders to trust, accept and acknowledge the existence, the value and knowledge created with the LHS.

Lastly, our ethics framework also captures the different phases of the ConcePTION project: towards the idea of an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people during the project proposal-phase, to the

development of an LHS during the project, to the responsible implementation of an LHS which represents the phase in which all insights are being collected and used for the development of a sustainable ecosystem. In all of these different phases, ethical deliberation was and still is included and resulted into this elaborate report.

Table 4 Ethics Framework

	Principle	Obligation
Towards the idea of an LHS	Solidarity	Pregnant and breastfeeding people should have a role in the generation of new knowledge on medication safety.
		Researchers, healthcare professionals, health institutions should bare the responsibility to help increase the awareness of the knowledge gap amongst people of childbearing age. With that they should explain how the collection of (health) data, the contribution to registries and biobanks, and research will help change the status quo for pregnant and breastfeeding people.
The development of an LHS	Justice, equity and responsiveness	Researchers, health institutions and data scientists should also act in solidarity and help with creating an appropriate infrastructure for contribution by people of childbearing age and their healthcare professionals.
		Researchers, healthcare professionals, data access providers, funders should respect the health interests of all pregnant and breastfeeding people.
Responsible implementation of an LHS	Respect for autonomy	Funders, research agenda setters, researchers should take care that the interests of pregnant people get equal weight in discussions about investments in knowledge generation of medication use.
		Researchers, healthcare professionals, data access providers, funders should be responsive to the health needs of pregnant and breastfeeding people
		Data access providers should be inclusive to the different health interests of pregnant people.
		Pregnant and breastfeeding people and healthcare professionals should be involved in the formulation of research questions in an LHS, to make sure these questions are responsive to the health needs of pregnant people.
		Researchers, healthcare professionals and health institutions should create ways to communicate new information in an understandable and respectful manner to pregnant and breastfeeding people.
		Regulators, healthcare professionals, pregnant and breastfeeding people should engage in the discussions of informed consent and in the translation of health information into data back into knowledge to improve clinical care.
Responsible implementation of an LHS	Trust, Transparency,	Regulators, data scientists, researchers should consider the type of use of the data as a metric for decisions regarding informed consent.
		Pregnant and breastfeeding people want to be informed about the type of use of their (health) data.
		Data access providers and health institutions should bare the responsibility for making sure informed consent is asked or that people are actually able to object to the collection of their (health) data.
		Researchers and data access providers should provide information to pregnant and breastfeeding people about why it is important to collect data and for what purposes are data going to be used
		A data access committee should be installed and should be responsible for making sure that data reuse has social value and low risk of foreseeable harm.
		Researchers, data access providers and others working within the LHS should be transparent about data collection, data analysis, public-private collaborations and the way privacy of pregnant

<p>and responsibility</p>	<p>and breastfeeding people is protected to earn trust and serve the interest of pregnant and breastfeeding people.</p> <p>Researchers, data access providers and health institutions should try to meet the expectations of pregnant and breastfeeding people regarding the use of their (health) data and keep informing them about progress made within the LHS.</p> <p>Transparency allows pregnant and breastfeeding people to take control and hold DAPs accountable.</p> <p>Transparency also means that management and organizational support should make governance structures accessible and visible for all contributing organizations. With that, enough resources should become available to develop accessible information about the LHS and research documentation that is easy to read by pregnant and breastfeeding people.</p> <p>A data access committee should be installed to provide guidance on conditions for data access, recognition, and supporting agreements.</p> <p>Data access providers should provide coherent information to pregnant and breastfeeding people and should make an effort in making data FAIR.</p>
<p>Sustainability</p>	<p>Researchers, healthcare professionals and health institutions should bare the responsibility to make sure that the learning in from an LHS is embedded in the practice of care, to improve the practice of care.</p> <p>All relevant stakeholders should accept and acknowledge the value and knowledge created with the LHS.</p>

2.2 Commentary on the ethics framework

2.2.1 Solidarity

When it comes to changing the way knowledge on medication safety is being generated, until now, the focus has mainly been on the role of research ethics committees, together with researchers, funding agencies, manufacturers, pharmacologist and guideline committees to safeguard the interests of pregnant and breastfeeding people in research (van der Zande et al., 2017). However, the role of pregnant and breastfeeding people in the generation of new knowledge has been left undiscussed.

Interestingly, for the group of rare disease patients, change in the way scientific knowledge is developed mainly comes from within the group itself. These patients have been able to unify, share experiences and change the way knowledge is being generated by putting themselves on the research agenda (Aymé et al., 2008). In the literature, this development in the context of rare diseases has been ascribed to solidarity (Mascalzoni et al., 2018; Woods, 2016). The question rises whether solidarity could play a similar role for pregnant and breastfeeding people. The group of pregnant and breastfeeding people is of course very different from the group of rare disease patients. First of all, pregnant people do not seem to unify and ask for attention for the issues in a similar way as rare disease patients do. Patient advocacy groups are virtually non-existent, understandably because of the temporary nature of a pregnancy. Furthermore, a pregnancy is of course not a disease, which means that the experience with being pregnant is not solely a medical, or even a challenging one. Lastly, in the literature it has been described that in general, people of childbearing potential seem to be not as much involved in clinical decisions during preconception that may have an impact on their fertility goals, or they are left unsupported in making such decisions, when also managing their chronic disease. As a result, they are less involved with and known to the problem and need for more evidence to support appropriate use of medication during pregnancy (Marques et al., 2020).

Despite these differences between the group of rare disease patients and pregnant people, solidarity may be of great importance for the group of pregnant and breastfeeding people and especially for the way knowledge on medications used during pregnancy and breastfeeding, is being generated. To realize change and to get pregnant and breastfeeding people involved, pregnant and breastfeeding people might need to be stimulated in becoming solidaristic. The question rises: is it possible to stimulate enactment of solidarity? In order to answer that question, we need to know more about the concept of solidarity.

The concept of solidarity

In the ethics literature, solidarity is often seen as a complex and multifaced concept. The aim of this analysis is not to add to the concepts of solidarity that exist, but to apply the existing philosophical literature to the situation of pregnant people. As such, we find that Barbara Prainsack and Alena Buyx (2017) have undertaken one of the most extended analyses of solidarity on both the normative understanding and the practical applicability of the concept. More explicitly, they developed a new approach to understand the concept of solidarity, which is explicit and allows for the formulation of clear conditions for actions that can be regarded as solidaristic. We find the practical applicability of their concept useful for the formulation of clear steps for the group of pregnant and breastfeeding people.

Prainsack and Buyx understand solidarity as “enacted commitments to accept costs to assist others with whom a person or persons recognize similarity in a relevant respect” (Prainsack & Buyx, 2017, p. 43). Important elements in this definition are that 1) solidarity is enacted and not just a general feeling, sentiment or attitude towards another person (like for example empathy and altruism), 2) solidarity involves a commitment and not something you do once (such as marching in a protest this one time), and 3) solidarity is based on the recognition of a similarity between individuals that matters in a specific situation (therefore, solidarity is context dependent) (pp. 52-54).

Furthermore, solidarity can take place on three different levels, also called the tiers of solidarity: 1) the individual level (between individuals), 2) the group level (between people who consider themselves bound together through at least one similarity, such as a shared medical condition), and 3) the institutionalized level (where solidarity is institutionalized in the shape of contracts, legal or administrative norms, such as societal welfare arrangements). In this analysis we mainly focus on solidarity on the individual or inter-personal level, since this is where we would want enactment of solidarity to take effect.

The normativity of solidarity

To understand whether enactment of solidarity can be stimulated, we need to understand the normative function of solidarity; we need to understand why we need a concept of solidarity in the situation of pregnant people and how solidarity can be used to change their status quo. For understanding the normative function, we have used the interpretation of Prainsack and Buyx and other literature that builds upon their understanding of solidarity.

In general, literature on solidarity does not seem to agree on the normative content of solidarity, and therefore, the normativity of solidarity is often seen as rather complex (Prainsack and Buyx, 2017; Dawson & Verweij, 2012; Kolers, 2021). Prainsack and Buyx analyzed the normative content in their book and explain that there are different explanations for how we can understand the normative strength of solidarity. However, they conclude that solidarity does not have a freestanding strength, but receives its normativity mainly from other values and principles. Solidarity can be understood as a “putty” (Prainsack and Buyx, 2017), a connector of some sort that connects general values with specific principles and values. More specifically, solidarity can help specify actions when a general (bioethical) value, like for example, justice or beneficence, does not tell us what to do or how to interpret the demands of justice or beneficence in a specific situation. Solidarity can also help with connecting people, individuals, or groups, who are not yet unified socially or morally, because

solidarity is often struggle specific and a response to a problem of division (Kolers, 2021). It does not mean that solidarity can by itself solve a problem, it relies on the individuals who are willing to connect and unite for the purpose of realizing the same goal through solidarity. Where general values like justice, autonomy, beneficence exist in a top-down manner, solidarity, especially at the inter-personal level, emerges bottom-up. The essence of solidarity is what people are willing to do in solidarity and what they want to commit to. Therefore, we should not be telling individuals that they need to act in solidarity with other people with whom we think they might share a similarity in a relevant respect, since that would defeat the whole purpose of solidarity. Solidarity is bound by the *voluntariness* of individuals to accept a cost to help someone with whom *they* recognize a similarity in a relevant respect (Prainsack and Buyx, 2017). Therefore, solidarity cannot be demanded and sanctioned in the way duties of justice can be demanded (Prainsack and Buyx, p. 78).

Fundamentally, solidarity receives its normative strength from other values and can help connect those values to specific actions. In the case of pregnant and breastfeeding people, the question arises: which bioethical value helps solidarity make more explicit?

Justice for pregnant people and their HCP

Most solutions for the lack of knowledge on medication safety in pregnancy focus on a principle of justice. As does this report, by focusing on the transformation to an LHS to stimulate equal access to medical advances and to just distribution of benefits. Avery Kolers, who has extensively studied the concept of solidarity, explains the function of solidarity in more detail and connects the concept of solidarity to the concept of justice as the following: “solidarity helps realize justice by empowering people to *claim* what they deserve” (Kolers, 2021, p.124). Kolers explains that we need a concept of solidarity because it can guide actions to realize justice. In this explanation, justice is the motivation for why we need people to act in solidarity. In turn, solidarity helps formulate actions that can help improve the situation for people from the perspective of justice. In order for people to act, people should be empowered, so that they can in fact claim what they need and deserve. Meaning that people should be given the tools and knowledge to be able to realize that they are in this shared situation that needs actions of solidarity to change the status quo.

As mentioned earlier, pregnant and breastfeeding people are not as much involved in clinical decision making regarding their pregnancy and might not be aware of the existing knowledge gap and their vulnerability resulting from it (Marques et al., 2020). Therefore, we believe that people of childbearing potential can change their status quo when they are given the tools and the knowledge they need to act in solidarity. Raising awareness about the issue of the lack of knowledge and the risks resulting from it, could be step one in stimulating any action of solidarity. A second step could be providing knowledge on how scientific research and learning from real-world data can help close the knowledge gap and, with that, it should become clear to people how they can engage in and contribute to closing the knowledge gap. Raising awareness and providing information about how pregnant people can be involved, might stimulate the recognition of a similarity in a relevant respect and may lead to solidaristic actions.

Figure 2 *Stimulating enactment of solidarity*

Activities

The question rises, what can people of childbearing potential actually do to help improve their own situation or the situation of future pregnant and breastfeeding people. As mentioned earlier, the lack of knowledge is a multi-stakeholder problem. Which means that the contribution of pregnant and breastfeeding people could also potentially stimulate the work of many different stakeholders. For example, to be able to learn from routinely collected health data in a learning healthcare system, there needs to be enough relevant data to analyze. To make sure that there is enough relevant data to analyze, it is important that pregnant people are aware of data collection and data analyses for the purpose of improving care and generating knowledge. And ideally, they show an interest in information about data collection in a meaningful manner.

For the ConcePTION ecosystem, there are also other ways of data collection that are useful for the generation of new knowledge that do require a more active role of pregnant and breastfeeding people. An example would be types of prospective cohort studies that collect data via surveys or other follow-up interventions. Another example, is reporting side-effects or other complications during a treatment. In this way, medications can be registered, and trends can be followed, which in turn can lead to further investigations on side-effects.

Besides data intensive research within the ConcePTION ecosystem, pregnant and breastfeeding people can participate in all sorts of research activities varying from clinical research to observational studies, or they can donate milk and blood samples for the purpose of future research activities in the ecosystem.

The activities mentioned above are very much focused on the participation of pregnant and breastfeeding people in research activities. Although the focus of our analysis is to stimulate the engagement of pregnant and breastfeeding people in closing the knowledge gap, there are also other type of activities that do not necessary influence research in a direct manner. As we have seen in the group of rare disease patients, patient representation in different institutes like hospitals, research ethics committees, and funding agencies, focused on the involvement, needs and demands of pregnant people could also be highly beneficial. These sorts of activities also require some sacrifice or time-investment from individuals for the sake of the group which could be seen as enactments of solidarity.

Empowerment

Now that we have an idea of what pregnant and breastfeeding people can do, in terms of activities that could both help close the knowledge gap and can be regarded as enactment of solidarity, we also need to think about ways to empower pregnant people. In order to raise awareness and to explain how their involvement and enactments of solidarity can help change their situation and the situation of future pregnant people, we need the support of many other important stakeholders. Not only do we

need pregnant and breastfeeding people to be more solidaristic, we also need HCPs, data scientists, funding agencies, registries and other professionals to become more solidaristic with pregnant and breastfeeding people. Their roles are crucial in raising awareness and building the right infrastructure to allow people to be more involved.

The task to empower people of childbearing potential so that they can become more solidaristic towards other people of childbearing potential is a one of great magnitude. Furthermore, we are aware that it might be difficult to encourage individual pregnant and breastfeeding people to act in solidarity for the sake of the whole group of pregnant and breastfeeding people. Therefore, we believe that raising awareness should also involve educating people early on, on all sorts of challenges people face during their pregnancy and on ways how they can help close the knowledge gap. Knowing about the challenges of medication used in pregnancy early on might increase the ability to recognize the similarity which is an important trigger for solidaristic action. With that, it might be important to be aware of the differences between people who are considered healthy and people who also have to deal with a chronic illness or condition during their pregnancy. These differences might also result in different triggers or reasons for why people want to act in solidarity. In general, the connection between people who share the same illness or condition is stronger (Prainsack & Buyx, 2017). However, these differences might also help with stimulating enactment of solidarity among pregnant people dealing with different type of illnesses or conditions.

At the same time, there are groups of pregnant people who are very active on online media, like pregnancy forums (Moravec, 2011). Here they share experiences with and ask questions to other people who are either pregnant or just gave birth. In a sense, there is already some sense of recognition and solidarity, but not in an efficient manner that can be used to systematically learn from.

Something that has not been discussed in this report is the question whose responsibility it is to empower pregnant people? As mentioned earlier, in the past, different type of stakeholders have been mentioned to safeguard the interests of pregnant people in research. Ideally, all stakeholders feel responsible in raising awareness about the lack of knowledge and help pregnant people find their way in acting in solidarity. However, this might result in an overall lack of initiative. For a project like ConcePTION, it could be useful to divide responsibilities of raising awareness and providing knowledge and tools to empower pregnant and breastfeeding people. Furthermore, it could be useful to inventorize which partner can reach what subgroup of people of childbearing potential.

2.2.2 Justice, equity and responsiveness

It is important to take an equity lens into account for knowledge generation for medication used by pregnant people, primarily because the current knowledge gap is the result of an unequal balance in the knowledge generation for pregnant people who use medication (van der Graaf et al., 2018). First, according to the formal principle of justice every human being should be treated equally, unless they differ in ways that are relevant to the situation in which they are involved. Justice for pregnant people thus first of all means that funders, research agenda setters and others should take care that the interests of pregnant people equalize, if not gain more weight in discussions about investments in knowledge generation of medication use. Furthermore, an equity lens means that pregnant people should be treated as equal to other people or groups who benefit from knowledge generation and their health interests should be respected without regard to age, gender, race, economic status, or ethnicity. Moreover, the terminology used for pregnant “women” matters. Until recently, it was common to talk about pregnant and breastfeeding “women”. Nowadays, more and more researchers within different disciplines have started to use pregnant “people” in stead of pregnant “women”. For example in a lot of recent literature on (the lack of) Covid-19 research with pregnant people and in the ethics literature authors have started to change the wording by using pregnant people. In the latest version of the guidance document *Ethical Considerations in HIV Prevention Trials*, the UNAIDS and the WHO use “women” and “gender-divers persons” to acknowledge that the group of pregnant people is broader and also includes trans people and non-binary people (2021, p.32). Ethically, the interests of pregnant people as a whole may even be more underrepresented, since for the different

subpopulations that fall under the group that has traditionally been labelled as pregnant women, even less knowledge has been developed. For example, for the group of transmen we know that although most have undergone surgeries during their transition, making pregnancy not possible, there are transmen who become pregnant and are in need of obstetric care. Besides the challenge of gaining access to healthcare due to discrimination, rejection of treatment, a lack of knowledge and cultural understanding on the part of health professionals, there is also no knowledge regarding the safety of hormone therapy, let alone in combination with a chronic disease or illness for pregnant transmen and their developing fetus. For transwomen it is not (yet) possible to become pregnant, however, there are ways for transwomen to develop breast tissue and to start hormone therapy to mimic the natural postpartum process. Again, the risks of these therapies for the infant remain unknown (García-Acosta et al., 2020). Furthermore, the ConcePTION project has been approached through social media by the LGBTQ+ community and was asked for a more inclusive lens, considering their health needs in the creation of a knowledge generating ecosystem. Taking an equity lens into account for knowledge generation for medication used in pregnancy and breastfeeding has become more apparent because of various calls for inclusivity of minorities in research. A recent example is, of course, Covid-19 research where minorities, vulnerable groups and pregnant people were underrepresented or not included. The exclusion of pregnant people in Covid vaccine research and the cautious attitude towards vaccinating pregnant people, had severe health consequences for many unvaccinated pregnant people.

Second, an equity lens may also be interpreted as a form of *corrective justice*, meaning that there is a moral need to prioritize the inclusion of minorities as long as their interests have been, and continue to be, underrepresented by the results of research. With prioritizing research initiatives for pregnant and breastfeeding people to help close the knowledge gap, could be a way of restoring their vulnerable position. An equity lens may also be interpreted as a form of *justice as equality*, meaning that for pregnant people specifically, extra attention for bias is essential in the context of health data research. Some databases are specifically directed to the health interests of pregnant people (such as *Lareb* in the Netherlands, *EFEMERIS* in France and *ENTIS*, the global collaborative network of Teratology Information Services). Other databases may consist of routine health care data for which it may be essential to check before using the database whether the database has been inclusive of their health interests.

Finally, an equity lens means that the research question that is raised in the context of health data research should be *responsive* to the health needs of pregnant and breastfeeding people, meaning that research and the research agenda should address their priorities and wishes. Also, in an LHS that is specifically created for pregnant and breastfeeding people it may be essential to consider the kind of knowledge that the system generates. Consequently, in an LHS those questions that have been raised will impact the feedback loop, and with that, the information that will be created. It is therefore important to identify biases early on to make sure the information flowing from the LHS is free from (or as much as possible) biases. To help identify these biases early on, patient representatives and healthcare professionals should be included in the formulation of research questions as much as possible. These stakeholders have valuable knowledge and ideas about what the health needs are of pregnant and breastfeeding people.

Furthermore, in research ethics, responsiveness and reasonable availability are closely related. Those whose interests are studied should also have reasonable access to the results. In an LHS, the dissemination of results can go in multiple ways, and therefore, not all results may immediately become available to all (relevant) stakeholders. Nonetheless, it is essential to create ways to communicate new information in an understandable and respectful manner. Meaning that a translation of new results is necessary for pregnant and breastfeeding people. Furthermore, during our interviews, it was emphasized that the role of the healthcare professional is important in both the search for and dissemination of information about medication and treatments for pregnant and breastfeeding people. Respondents even argued that regardless of an LHS, they would still rather rely on the information from the HCP, because they know more about their specific condition and their

specific health needs. With that, most respondents expressed the wish for personalized information, because they are aware that medication safety and efficacy could differ among individuals.

2.2.3 Respect for autonomy

There is clear political will in many countries to try to maximize data intensive research under the banner of Big Data or LHSs, however, this type of research creates a set of problems regarding the interests and autonomy of data subjects. Protecting or respecting the individual interests and autonomy of data subjects is challenging, and it is often unclear how data subjects should give consent for the secondary use of their health data for research. Furthermore, various research activities in an LHS might require various kinds of consent. Therefore, consent reform is often considered to be part and parcel of LHS transformation (Wouters et al., 2021). However, a gap still exists between the theoretical ideal and pragmatic and regulatory reality of an LHS: who must request consent, what type of learnings require consent, where would a waiver be appropriate, when do we still need consent, and how to administer such consent? Spector-Bagdady and Jagsi (2018) argue that to find an answer to these questions, requires the commitment of healthcare professionals, the input of patients and the willingness of regulators. Their engagement is necessary in defining boundaries for data intensive research and in translating health information into data back into knowledge for optimizing clinical intervention (Spector-Bagdady & Jagsi, 2018).

When informed consent?

Regarding the question when informed consent should be asked, there are different interpretation. For example, Faden and colleagues called for a new ethical balancing of priorities based on invasiveness of research (2013), while regulators often focus on the sensitivity of data. However, among HCPs and patients, type of use is often more cited as a concern and might be a better metric for making decisions regarding informed consent (Spectator-Bagdady & Jagsi, 2018). During our interviews, most respondents argued that it is important to at least notify people about collecting and using health data and especially about the goal for which data are being used. A small group of respondents argued for a more active role since they wanted to give informed consent for the use of their health data for a study within an LHS. They argued that giving consent would allow for some control about what is being done with one's own data. According to these respondents, data are something personal that should be treated with caution. Other respondents argued that giving informed consent every time a new study is performed with their data is too invasive and could negatively influence a person's willingness to contribute. Being (re)contacted for research was sometimes experienced as annoying and was not considered a priority. Furthermore, respondents put forward that when data is anonymous, then there is no added personal value in knowing or giving consent. Furthermore, multiple respondents suggested that when an LHS has been developed it would suffice to have a clear statement on the website explaining how and by whom data is collected, analyzed, and stored. Having information available online allows people to look for the information when they want to know more.

Who asks for informed consent?

Within an LHS like ConcePTION, it is important that the collaborating organizations individually arrange the informed consent procedure properly. Organizations that collect and store health data have a responsibility to make sure informed consent is asked or pregnant and breastfeeding people are actually able to object to the collection of their health data. With that, information on how to give consent or how to object to the collection of health data needs to be provided. Giving information can, for example, be done during a consult, through the website of the collecting organization, notification via email or other type of communication platform, a information leaflet send by the collecting organization. Furthermore, with the information on how to give informed consent or how to object, it should be made clear why it is important to collect data and why it cannot be done in a different way. Again, there is a difference between organizations that either actively collect data through surveys or registries, and organizations that use data from routinely collected health data from hospitals. However, as done in other type of research, it should be made clear to pregnant and breastfeeding people why it is important to share their data.

Next, from our own interviews, as well as from the literature, it becomes clear that transparency regarding type of use and regarding data sharing: with whom is the data, either pseudoanonymized or anonymized, going to be shared and for what purposes? To make sure data is not being used for purposes that are not in line with personal values and goals of pregnant and breastfeeding people, it is important to explain to pregnant and breastfeeding people for what purposes and in what ways their data are used. Giving them the tools and knowledge concerning data collection, also enables people to communicate why they would not want to share their data and empowers them to hold data controllers accountable for misuse of their data.

Lastly, to create a level of accountability for the way respect for autonomy of pregnant and breastfeeding people is being handled within the LHS, there should be a Data Access Committee (DAC) or other type of governance body installed. A DAC could make sure data reuse has potential social value and that there is low risk of foreseeable harms (Cheah & Piasecki, 2020). To promote data sharing and to motivate data subjects, DACs should encourage secondary uses that are in line with the interests of data subjects and the organizations that collect data. A DAC or similar type of governance body would review both applications of organization wanting to make use of the LHS and should establish frameworks with clear lines of accountability, terms of reference and membership (Cheah & Piasecki, 2020).

2.2.4 Trust, transparency and responsibility

While the prospects of data intensive research within an LHS are exciting, from an ethical perspective a central issue rises: how to earn and maintain trust of patients and their families and other relevant stakeholders, when sensitive data are being used for secondary purposes, that is, purposes beyond the welfare of the individual (Botkin, 2017). Trust is proven to be essential for the development and success of a sustainable LHS. Both in our literature search and our interview study, trust is often discussed in relation to transparency and responsibility. Most of our respondents argued that transparency is of great importance for the sustainability of an LHS and for earning their trust in such a system. Respondents of our interview study explained that to be transparent includes honesty about data collection, data analyses, public-private partnerships, and the way privacy is protected. Transparency also makes the information that flows from it seem more reliable and solid, because it shows that there is “nothing to hide” and all relevant information on how the LHS works is available to anyone who is interested. Furthermore, our respondents explained that they trust researchers to handle data correctly and that they trust researchers to follow the rules and regulations regarding data protection. Some respondents argued that because they trust researchers, they do not need to be informed about every detail of the research project.

In the literature, it is emphasized that it is important to meet the public expectations for transparency when developing an LHS, which in turn will strengthen or maintain trust in not alone the LHS, but also the institutions working within the LHS (Botkin, 2017). People expect their voluntary contribution to be of use to improve the care of others, and that their good faith will not be exploited. Much depends, therefore, on the extent to which uses of personal data are seen as serving the public interest and conducted by those with a public interest orientation. It is of great importance that an LHS fully addresses these features in order to realize transparency, increase responsibility and earn trust of the public (Carter et al., 2014). A way to realize such a balance between the expectations of pregnant and breastfeeding people and the aims of research within the LHS, is to include lay representatives in the LHS to think along. With that, it is important to keep informing pregnant and breastfeeding people about what is happening and what progress is being made in terms of knowledge generation on medication safety.

Moreover, transparency is already mandatory by law under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Article 5.1.a). In the GDPR, transparency is one of the main principles in personal data processing and is translated into the requirement that any information and communication relating to the processing of those personal data to be easily accessible and easy to understand, and that clear

and plain language is to be used. The Data Protection Working Party, makes the term transparency more concrete by adding the goals of engendering trust in the process which affect the people by enabling them to understand, and if necessary, challenge those practices (Article 29 DPW, 2018, p.4). In this understanding, transparency can empower data subjects to hold data controllers and processors accountable and to exercise control over their personal data by, for example, withdrawing their informed consent. This description reflects transparency in research applications on human subjects, which refers to being open about the process, outcomes and entailed risks of a study (Rossi & Lenzi, 2020). Accomplishing transparency may come with some resistance since it requires significant architectural changes (Spagnuolo et al., 2019). With that, transparency raises the question of responsibility. In an LHS, with different stakeholders from different countries, the question arises: who is responsible for making sure duties of transparency are met and what information should be enclosed to which stakeholder? Ideally, in an LHS with different partnering organizations, each institutions installs proper structures for realizing transparency. However, not all organizations within or contributing to the LHS, are similar in the sense that they have the same institutions in place. Therefore, duties of transparency should be communicated beforehand with all relevant stakeholders or should be discussed in relation to the sustainability of the LHS.

Some of the literature focusses on a narrow understanding of transparency, namely the user-centric view, which states that transparency is important so that users can be empowered to hold data processors accountable for the usage and the processing of the user's personal data (Spagnuolo et al., 2019). The user-centric view is also translated into the GDPR as described earlier. However, in the context of governance, transparency also refers to the accessibility and visibility of the governance structures. Within a consortium, for example, good governance requires that those internal or external to the project know what governance structures and procedures are in place, what mechanisms for legitimate decision-making have been adopted, and where authority and responsibility for different types of actions are located in the consortium (Morrison et al., 2020). The complexity of transparency is amplified by the institutional and organizational fragmentation of the LHS, which is not a single unitary public organization or the like. This governance interpretation of transparency is also applicable to the context of an LHS with different partnering organizations contributing to the LHS. For both the research activities within the LHS and the development of new information, it is important that organizations know what data should be enclosed to which stakeholder, how personal data should be processed, what methods are being used to store, analyse and interpret data. Furthermore, it is also important to create a clear structure regarding who has authority over what and who is responsible for what. A DAC, as explained under the principle of respect for autonomy, could also help to provide guidelines on specific conditions for data collection, access and sharing, but also on recognition requirements such as authorships, acknowledgements, citations and collaboration (agreements). Furthermore, a DAC could mandate when formal data access agreements should be signed and whether cost sharing mechanisms are to be put in place (Cheah & Piasecki, 2020).

As mentioned earlier, installing proper structures to realize transparency might come with some resistance and achieving meaningful transparency is also not easy. Key elements to overcome resistance and challenges, are: 1) to ensure there is sufficient budget and human resource time allocate to develop accessible information about the LHS and research documentation that is easy to read and to understand; with the right balance between candor and reassurance, 2) data controllers should provide coherent information to data subjects and should make the effort in making the data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). With that, lay representatives (ideally drawn from the group of pregnant and breastfeeding people, who may well reflect the level of literacy and experience from their own situation) are a good sounding board for the coherence of information provided by data controllers as well as a sounding board for scientific or legal information (Morrison et al., 2020).

One last note about transparency: not all people want to be informed all the time. Or not everything is of interest to them. In our interviews, respondents mentioned that it is not so much that they want to receive every detail of information, however, they want to know where to go when they want to read more information. Knowing there is a place (probably the internet) where there is potentially an answer

to every question you have about your personal data in an LHS, is most important. With that, it was mentioned that it is important that the reason for which their data is being used, is something they would support. Furthermore, respondents argued that it is important that their data are not being used for other purposes of which they were not informed or are not mentioned in a statement on a leaflet or website regarding the research and aim of research. Some respondents also expressed a cautious attitude towards public-private partnerships in an LHS. According to them, private organizations have an additional goal, namely to make a profit from research with their data, which in turn jeopardizes the neutrality of the information and negatively influences their trust in that system, and therefore, in the information that flows from that system. Transparency about all the different types of aims organizations can have to contribute to the LHS, and transparency about collaborating with private organizations seems important from the perspective of data subjects.

2.2.5 Sustainability

Sustainability (from an ethical point of view) is in two ways related to LHSs. Essential for LHSs is that learning is embedded in the practice of care, while simultaneously, the results of the embedded learning activities improve the practice of care. Some LHSs start as forms where care and research are aligned by more efficient ways in which can be learned from routinely collected data. But when these systems mature as a healthcare system, results that the system creates should also be returned to the target population of the system (Wouters, et al., 2021). For an LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people, at some point in time, the knowledge created must also be made available for them and their healthcare providers. In that way, results of the embedded learning activities can actually improve the practice of care, from which we can learn subsequently.

When LHSs mature, it will be essential that stakeholders recognize and embrace the need for and the added value of the system itself. Beyond a project phase, patients, physicians, scientists, boards of directors, data managers, health institutions, pharmaceutical companies, governments and others should be convinced of the need of this system as an added or new way forward to create knowledge and to accept the value of the knowledge that this system creates. Pregnant people should be empowered to see the added value of participation in the system and contribute by means of data sharing, physicians should explain why data sharing is important, hospital managers and database owners should help to make the data FAIR and put governance systems in place to maintain trust in the learning health system, health authorities should acknowledge the social value of the knowledge created, especially when an LHS has proven to be a valuable alternative to clinical trials.

3.1 ConcePTION as a Learning Healthcare System

As mentioned earlier, the structure of ConcePTION is similar to what is being called a learning healthcare system in the literature. To understand what ConcePTION might look like as an LHS, we developed a diagram that visualizes the potential processes and flows in the ConcePTION ecosystem (see figure 3).

Figure 3 diagram of the ConcePTION Ecosystem

Explanation of the ConcePTION ecosystem

This diagram contains different elements that could exist in the ConcePTION ecosystem, it also captures the flows, learning activities or products of certain processes, and it shows a closed loop which represents one of the most important features of an LHS: namely the improvement of (clinical) practice and learnings from real-world data.

A way to interpret this ecosystem is as follows: let us start with a research question formulated or initiated by pregnant and breastfeeding people and/ or their HCPs, researchers, physicians, the pharmaceutical industry, or Data Access Providers (DAPs), regarding the effects of a certain treatment or the course of a certain type of illness during pregnancy. To answer this research question through the ConcePTION ecosystem, a method for data analysis needs to be developed, as well as an inventory of what is needed to answer the question and who will have access to valuable information to answer the research question. The method will also include important variables, dates etc. and will contain an algorithm that can be used by all the DAPs to locally analyze their data for this specific research question.

After the algorithm has been sent and the analyses have been run by the DAPs, the results of the analyses will be sent to and shared in a research dashboard, accessible to researchers or other stakeholders. The research dashboard can be used to interpret the results from the data analyses. After the interpretation of results there are multiple possible routes within the ecosystem (these are not mutually exclusive): 1) the interpretation of results could lead to a scientific publication which will answer the research question and can be accessed through PubMed by the scientific community and researcher-physicians, 2) the interpretation of results can be used as new knowledge for the public knowledge bank (created by ConcePTION), which will be able to help answer safety questions from people and their HCPs, 3) the interpretation of results leads to a new research question that could be answered with the help of the ConcePTION network, 4) the interpretation of results can lead to a direct implementation of results in and change to clinical practice. In this last flow, new results are directly implemented in daily practice and will lead to new health data, which at a later stage can be used in data analyses within the ConcePTION ecosystem. The last flow represents a true model 2 LHS, represented in figure 4.

Figure 4 the healthcare system flow

3.2 The ConcePTION Ecosystem and the Ethics Framework

(Research) Question

Once the ConcePTION Ecosystem has been established, it can be used to answer all sorts of research questions. These questions can either be posed by a researcher or a HCP out of scientific interest, or these questions can be the result of a safety question asked by for example a pregnant person, or someone who wants to become pregnant and wants to know whether her medication is safe.

To earn trust in the value of the research being conducted within the ecosystem, it is important that pregnant and breastfeeding people are aware of how the ecosystem works, but also that they can give input to what type of questions are answered with the help of the ecosystem. With that, it should be made possible for people to object to research questions or collaborations that are, according to them, not in line with their personal interests or values. Or that at least, their consent is asked for the type of use of their data for certain types of research questions. Furthermore, it is important that these questions are in line with the principles of justice, equity and that they are responsive to the health interests and needs of all pregnant and breastfeeding people, without regard to age, gender, race, economic status, or ethnicity.

Analysis of local data

An important and unique feature of the ConcePTION ecosystem is the way data is being processed and analyzed locally by the DAPs. The different types of DAPs and the data they represent are illustrated by the beeswax structure. They coexist, but do not share raw data from their databases. They also conduct the analyses locally with their own database or the data they have access to.

ConcePTION should help with developing ways to empower pregnant and breastfeeding people to be more actively involved and to make sure they contribute to data collection in a valuable manner. Raising awareness about the knowledge gap and providing information about the way learning from real-world data could help close the knowledge gap are an important first step.

Moreover, DAPs should strive to make the processes of data collection, storage and analyses as transparent as possible to other stakeholders, including pregnant and breastfeeding people. In turn, ConcePTION could provide clear information on how data is being collected, stored and analyzed on the ConcePTION website. With that, DAPs have the responsibility to make sure informed consent is asked or that there is a way for people to object to data collection or analysis. If the DAP is not the organization responsible for data collection, it is also their responsibility to check whether informed consent is asked properly and people have the opportunity to object to data collection.

Research dashboard

The research dashboard is where the results of the data analyses come together. The way this dashboard works is still work in progress. For the presentation of results, again, the principles of justice and equity are important as well as the responsiveness to the health needs of pregnant and breastfeeding people. Also, in light of transparency, responsibility and respect for autonomy of data subjects, it should be made clear to all stakeholders, who has access to the research dashboard or to whom access is granted. For pregnant and breastfeeding people, it should be clear which (type of) organizations have access to results at which stage of research. Especially in a public-private collaboration, pregnant and breastfeeding people and their HCP want to know who has access to their data and on what level.

Interpretation of results

After the results of data analyses are made available through the research dashboard, stakeholders can start interpreting these results. For the interpretation of results, the principles of justice, equity and responsiveness are again extremely important. With that, it is important that HCPs and lay representatives are consulted to make sure the interpretation is useful to HCPs and pregnant and breastfeeding people. Also, in light of transparency, responsibility, sustainability, and scientific validity, it should be made clear what methods are used to interpret results.

Dissemination of results

As mentioned in the description of the infographic, the interpretation of results can lead to different flows. Important here, is that results also flow back to pregnant and breastfeeding people, their HCP, and regulators to really change clinical practice and to provide valuable information to stimulate informed decision-making. From our interviews, it became clear that pregnant and breastfeeding people want to have a clear answer to their health questions and that they would like to discuss these questions and safety information with their HCP, to make sure the information is also applicable to their specific situation. For the dissemination of results, the wish and expectations of pregnant and breastfeeding people should be taken into account.

Concluding remarks

In this report, we shared our ethics framework for a learning healthcare system for pregnant and breastfeeding people. The development of an ethically sound LHS is not without challenges. To respond to these challenges, we developed a framework, based on empirical and conceptual research. Our framework contains important ethical principles that can help guide the development of an ethically responsible and sustainable LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people. In our framework, we put emphasis on the principles of solidarity, justice, equity and responsiveness, respect for autonomy, trust, transparency and responsibility and sustainability. We also explain the importance of a change in the way knowledge is being generated, and how the development of an LHS can overcome current struggles in knowledge generation for pregnant and breastfeeding people. In order for this change of systems to work, all relevant stakeholders should be informed about the development towards an LHS, in which care and research are more aligned. It is essential that all

stakeholders support the idea that we need to change the current paradigm and that they accept the value of the knowledge that an LHS creates. Of course it takes time to develop such learning healthcare system, but when these systems mature, the knowledge created within this system must also be made available for pregnant and breastfeeding people and their healthcare providers. In that way, results of the embedded learning activities can actually improve the practice of care, from which we can learn subsequently.

We hope that the ethics framework can be used by the ConcePTION network for the development of a sustainable and ethically responsible ecosystem of continuous learning for pregnant and breastfeeding people.

References

- Adam MP, Polifka JE, Friedman JM. Evolving knowledge of the teratogenicity of medications in human pregnancy. *Am J Med Genet Part C Semin Med Genet.* 2011;157(3):175–82.
- Amsterdam UMC. Onderzoek gestaat met medicijn tegen groeivertraging ongeboren baby. [internet]. Available from : <https://amsterdamumc.org/nl/vandaag/onderzoek-gestaakt-met-medicijn-tegen-groeivertraging-ongeboren-baby-.htm>
- Aymé S, Kole A, Groft S. Empowerment of patients: lessons from the rare diseases community. *Lancet.* 2008;371(9629):2048–51.
- Basole RC, Braunstein ML, Sun J. Data and analytics challenges for a learning healthcare system. *J Data Inf Qual.* 2015;6(2–3):10–3.
- Baylis F. Pregnant women deserve better. *Nature.* 2010;465(7299):689–90.
- Baylis, F, Ballantyne, A. *Clinical research involving pregnant women (Vol. 3).* Springer. 2017.
- Beauchamp, TL, Childress, JF. *Principles of biomedical ethics.* Oxford University Press, USA. 2001.
- Botkin JR. Transparency and choice in learning healthcare systems. *Learn Heal Syst.* 2018;2(1):1–6.
- Brody H, Miller FG. The Research-Clinical Practice Distinction, Learning Health Systems, and Relationships. *Hastings Cent Rep.* 2013;43(5):41–7.
- Browne J, Van Der Zande I, Van Smeden M, Van Der Graaf R. Protect pregnant women by including them in clinical research. *BMJ [Internet].* 2018;362:9–11. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/doi:10.1136/bmj.k4013>
- Charmaz K. *Constructing Grounded theory: a practical guide through qualitative analysis:* SAGE Publications; 2006.
- Cheah PY, Piasecki J. Data Access Committees. *BMC Med Ethics.* 2020;21(1):1–8.
- Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences & World Health Organization. *CIOMS Guidelines. International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans.* [Internet]. 2016. Available from: <https://cioms.ch/publications/product/international-ethical-guide-lines-for-health-related-research-involving-humans/>.
- Cribb A, Entwistle V, Mitchell P. What does quality' add? Towards an ethics of healthcare improvement. *J Med Ethics.* 2020;46(2):118–22.
- Dawson A, Verweij M. Solidarity: A moral concept in need of clarification. *Public Health Ethics.* 2012;5(1):1–5.
- Faden RR, Kass NE, Goodman SN, Pronovost P, Tunis S, Beauchamp TL. An Ethics Framework for a Learning Health Care System: A Departure from Traditional Research Ethics and Clinical Ethics. *Hastings Cent Rep.* 2013;43(SUPPL. 1).
- Foley T, Fairmichael F. The Potential of Learning Health Care Systems. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2015;66(5):4–19.

- García-Acosta JM, Juan-Valdivia RMS, Fernández-Martínez AD, Lorenzo-Rocha ND, Castro-Peraza ME. Trans* pregnancy and lactation: A literature review from a nursing perspective. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(1):1–12.
- van der Graaf R, van der Zande ISE, den Ruijter HM, Oudijk MA, van Delden JJM, OudeRengerink K, et al. Fair inclusion of pregnant women in clinical trials: An integrated scientific and ethical approach. *Trials*. 2018;19(1):1–9.
- van der Graaf R, van der Zande ISE, van Delden JJM. How the CIOMS guidelines contribute to fair inclusion of pregnant women in research. *Bioethics*. 2019;33(3):367–73.
- Hollestelle MJ, van der Graaf R, Hartman SD, Sturkenboom MCJM, van Delden JJM. A Learning Healthcare System for pregnant and breastfeeding women: what do women during preconception, pregnancy, and nursing think? – A qualitative study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* [Internet]. 2022;22(1):1–12. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-022-04675-2>
- Innovative Medicine Initiative ConcePTION. Description: Key objectives of the project. [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.imi-conception.eu/description/>.
- Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS and the World Health Organization. Ethical Considerations in HIV Prevention Trials. Published January 27, 2021. [Internet] <https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/documents/2021/ethical-considerations-in-hiv-prevention-trials>.
- Kalkman S, van Delden J, Banerjee A, Tyl B, Mostert M, van Thiel G. Patients' and public views and attitudes towards the sharing of health data for research: a narrative review of the empirical evidence. *J Med Ethics*. 2022;48(1):3-13. doi:10.1136/medethics-2019-105651
- Kolers A. What does solidarity do for bioethics? *J Med Ethics*. 2021;47(2):122–8.
- Krubiner CB, Hyder AA. A bioethical framework for health systems activity: a conceptual exploration applying 'systems thinking.' *Heal Syst*. 2014;3(2):124–35.
- Macklin R. Enrolling pregnant women in biomedical research. *Lancet* [Internet]. 2010;375(9715):632–3. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)60257-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)60257-7)
- Marques SC, Wait S, Murphy M. Achieving optimal care for women of childbearing age living with chronic diseases: a policy report. 2020. London: The Health Policy Partnership.
- Mascalzoni D, Petrini C, Taruscio D, Gainotti S. The role of solidarity(-ies) in rare diseases research. *Adv Exp Med Biol*. 2017;1031(November 2018):589–604.
- Mclennan S, Kahrass H, Wieschowski S, Strech D, Langhof H. The spectrum of ethical issues in a Learning Health Care System: A systematic qualitative review. *Int J Qual Heal Care*. 2018;30(3):161–8.
- Moloney RM, Tambor ES, Tunis SR. Patient and clinician support for the learning healthcare system: Recommendations for enhancing value. *J Comp Eff Res*. 2016;5(2):123–8.
- Morrison M, Mourby M, Gowans H, Coy S, Kaye J. Governance of research consortia: challenges of implementing Responsible Research and Innovation within Europe. *Life Sci Soc Policy*. 2020;16(1):1–19.

- Prainsack B, Buyx A. *Solidarity in Biomedicine and Beyond*. (Cambridge Bioethics and Law), editor. *Solidarity in Biomedicine and Beyond*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2017.
- Roes KCB, van der Zande ISE, van Smeden M, van der Graaf R. Towards an appropriate framework to facilitate responsible inclusion of pregnant women in drug development programs. *Trials*. 2018;19(1):1–9.
- Rossi A, Lenzini G. Transparency by design in data-informed research: A collection of information design patterns. *Comput Law Secur Rev [Internet]*. 2020;37:105402. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2020.105402>
- Spagnuolo D, Ferreira A, Lenzini G. Accomplishing transparency within the general data protection regulation. *ICISSP 2019 - Proc 5th Int Conf Inf Syst Secur Priv*. 2019;(Icissp):114–25.
- Spector-Bagdady K, Jaggi R. Big data, ethics, and regulations: Implications for consent in the learning health system. *Med Phys*. 2018;45(10):e845–7.
- Steels S, Van Staa T. Evaluation protocol of the implementation of a learning healthcare system in clinical practice: The Connected Health Cities programme in the north of England. *BMJ Open*. 2019;9(6).
- Swan SH. Intrauterine exposure to diethylstilbestrol: Long-term effects in humans. *Apmis*. 2001;109(s103):210–22.
- van Thiel GJMW, van Delden JJM. Reflective equilibrium as a normative empirical model. *Ethical Perspect* 2010;17:183–202.
- Woods S. *Big Data Governance: Solidarity and the Patient Voice*. 2016;221–38.
- Wouters RHP, van der Graaf R, Voest EE, Bredenoord AL. Learning health care systems: Highly needed but challenging. *Learn Heal Syst*. 2020;(June 2019):1–6.
- Wouters RHP, van der Graaf R, Rigter T, Bunnik EM, Ploem MC, de Wert GMWR, et al. Towards a responsible transition to learning healthcare systems in precision medicine: Ethical points to consider. *J Pers Med*. 2021;11(6):1–11.
- van der Zande ISE, van der Graaf R, Oudijk MA, van Delden JJM. Vulnerability of pregnant women in clinical research. *J Med Ethics*. 2017;43(10):657–63.
- van der Zande ISE, van der Graaf R, Oudijk MA, van Delden JJM. How Should the Precautionary Principle Apply to Pregnant Women in Clinical Research? *J Med Philos*. 2021;46(5):516–29.